

Professionalism and Work Performance of Commissioned Officers: The Mediating Role of Work Values

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Abstract:- The main focus of this research is to measure the professionalism and work performance of the commissioned officer: the mediating role of work values. The study was conducted out using non-experimental quantitative research methodology employing the descriptive-correlational approach using Mean, Pearson r, Regression, and Sobel z-test as statistical tools. Mediation analysis was used as an approach in data analysis. Mediation model was used to find and explain the mechanism or process that underlying an observed connection between independent variables which is the professionalism and a dependent variable which is the work performance by introducing a third explanatory variable, known as a mediator variable which is the work values. The research instrument utilized were customized and being appropriated to the needs of the current study. The information was gathered using a stratified random sampling approach, with 300 police non-commissioned officers serving as respondents. The study found a substantial association between professionalism and work performance. Likewise, work values also show significant role. It also revealed that there is mediating effect of work values of police commissioned officers on the relationship between professionalism and work performance and partial mediation occurred on this study.

Keywords:- Criminal Justice Education, Professionalism, Work Performance, Work Values, Correlation, Path Analysis, Sobel Z-Test, Mediation, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

The Philippine National Police (PNP) has seen and endured some of the most difficult situations that have jeopardized the whole organization on several occasions in the recent years. Staying afloat was difficult due to a deteriorating public image and a performance that was deemed to be at its lowest point in the company's history. With accusations of police inefficiency, harming the morale of the majority of officers, the top brass had no choice but to go forward with a work-in-progress of reform to restore its proper position as the people's defender, as stipulated by Republic Act 8551 (Lobete, 2016).

Enforcing the law, preventing and controlling crime, maintaining public order, ensuring public safety and internal security, all while enlisting community participation and cooperation Philippine society is now confronted with a slew of challenges and concerns in the areas of economics, social welfare, and politics. As new problems emerge, such as terrorism, poverty, bureaucracy, and other socio-political and socio-economic difficulties, it is important to be vigilant. The Philippine National Police (PNP) is tasked by our constitution to ensure the welfare of all citizens (Vila, 2006).

Professionalism does not mean just wearing a suit, leading a team, or obtaining an advanced academic degree. It entails expressing the values of responsibility, integrity, excellence, and accountability, at all times, because all jobs across different industries will always require one thing for you to advance and move ahead in your career: a high degree of professionalism and ethical behaviour. Having strong work values indicates that the individual attaches great importance to the accomplishment of goals, to the treatment of people and to the conduct of one's business. Professionalism is a component of the idea of work values, which characterizes how a person approaches his or her job and conducts himself or herself while on the job (Lynch, 2009).

Conflicting and overlapping criteria theories, along with a lack of construct clarity as a consequence, have made it more difficult to comprehend the nature and theoretical foundations of the constructions of work performance. It should be noted that this is simply one part of the issue. To address to this problem, there are ways that can help police commissioned officers to improve themselves. This also helps identify the work performance of Commissioned Officers in the Province of Agusan del Sur. The main goal of this is to know the work performance of the Commissioned Officers in their duties and responsibilities in the province of Agusan del Sur. This study also aims to improve the attitude of the Police Commissioned Officers towards their duties and responsibilities in dealing with their subordinates. Commissioned Officers need to be responsive to a new information and work with researchers to measure what matters to their constituents.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study adopted the descriptive-correlational research design. Research that is descriptive in nature explains the attitudes and behaviors of those who participated in the inquiry, while research that is correlational in nature seeks to uncover statistical links between two factors (Vanderstoep & Johnston, 2009). It is an evidence study that allows researchers to examine the characteristics, behavioural patterns, and perspectives of study participants (Shuttleworth, 2008). Descriptive research is applicable in this study since it provides information about the current status of the occurrences to be described (Shuttleworth, 2008), and it is a realization study that allows researchers to examine the characteristics, behaviors, and perspectives of study participants. (Calmorin, 2007).

In addition, in this research, mediation analysis had been used to measure the causal process by which a preceding variable produces a mediating variable, which in turn causes a dependent variable, as well as the relationship between the two variables. However, although analysis is important in observational research, it is arguably most persuasive when it comes to addressing concerns about action and reaction in controlled treatment and preventive programs (MacKinnon, & Valente, 2019).

Moreover, an example of a non-experimental research approach, the correlational design, is one that aids researchers in establishing a link between two strongly related variables. When analyzing a link between two separate variables, there are no assumptions made, and statistical analysis methods are used to compute the correlation between different variables. According to the findings of this research, the degrees of professionalism, workplace values, and ability to do the job of the commissioned law enforcement officers were determined. Investigations were also carried out on the mediating influence of work values on the link between professionalism and job performance of Commissioned Police Officers.

Professionalism Questionnaire developed by Makeda, K. A. (2009) was used which was modified to fit the study and subjected to the validation of the experts. The Professionalism questionnaire had the (5) *indicator, namely: leader/communicator, Leader/Conflict resolver, Positive/Goal oriented, Worker/Prepared, and Miscellaneous*. In evaluating professionalism, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions was used as follows:

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Measures of professionalism are always Manifested
3.40 – 4.19	High	Measures of professionalism are often manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Measures of professionalism are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Measures of professionalism are seldom manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Measures of professionalism are never manifested

The questionnaire for work performance was adopted from Registe(2017). It was modified to fit in to the study and was subjected to the validation of the experts. The questionnaire for the work performance had the following indicators namely: *Task performance, Contextual performance and Counterproductive work behavior*.

In evaluating work performance, the following range of means with its descriptions was used.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Measures of work performance are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	High	Measures of work performance are often manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Measures of work performance are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Measures of work performance are seldom manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Measures of work performance are never manifested

The work values questionnaire was adopted from Smith (1971). It was modified to fit in to the study and subjected to the validation of the experts.

In evaluating the work values, the following range of means with its descriptions was used.

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Measures of work values are always manifested
3.40 – 4.19	High	Measures of work values are often manifested
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Measures of work values are sometimes manifested
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Measures of work values are seldom manifested
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Measures of work values are never manifested

The first draft of the survey instrument was delivered to the research adviser for comments, ideas, and recommendations to enhance its presentation. Final copies were refined by an experienced group. Before collecting data, experienced validators provided corrections, comments, and recommendations. It was determined that the items had a Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient of 0.886 or strong reliability after being piloted with 40 respondents. After which, the research adviser approved the distribution of the questionnaires to the respondents of the study.

Also, for more comprehensive interpretation and analysis of the data, the following statistical tools were utilized.

Average Weighted Mean. This will be used to compute and describe the level of professionalism and work

performance on work values of the Police Commissioned Officers.

Pearson Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation (r). This statistical tool was employed to determine the significance of the relationship of professionalism and work performance of the Police Commissioned Officers (PCOs) in the Province of Agusan del Sur.

Multiple Regression Analysis. This statistical tool was be used to measure the influence professionalism and work performance of the Commissioned Officers.

Medgraph using Sobel z-test. This statistical tool was be employed to determine the mediating effect of work values of Police Commissioned Officers on the relationship between professionalism and work performance.

III. RESULTS

The outputs of the set of data were presented and ordered based on the objectives of this study. First, to ascertain the level of professionalism of the commissioned officers; Second, to assess the level of work performance of the commissioned officers; Third, to describe the extent of work values among the subordinates; Fourth, to determine the significant relationship between professionalism and work performance; and finally, to determine the significance of mediating role of work values on the relationship between professionalism and work performance.

➤ *Level of Professionalism*

Shown in Table 1 is the Level of Professionalism of commissioned officers in the province of Agusan del Sur. The standard deviation was less than 1.00 which signified consistency of responses among the respondents. The overall mean score was 4.42 with a very high descriptive level. Scrutinizing the individual results of the level of professionalism of commissioned officers on the following indicators were as follows: Leader/Communicator has a mean of 4.39 described as very high, Leader/Conflict Resolver has a mean of 4.40 with a descriptive level of very high, Positive/Goal Oriented has a mean of 4.45 characterized as very high, and Worker/Prepared has a mean of 4.40 described as very high, Miscellaneous has a mean of 4.45 described as very high.

Table 1
Level of professionalism of the Commissioned Officers

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Leader/Communicator	0.64	4.39	Very High
Leader/Conflict Resolver	0.65	4.40	Very High
Positive/Goal Oriented	0.64	4.45	Very High
Worker/Prepared	0.63	4.40	Very High
Miscellaneous	0.67	4.45	Very High
Overall	0.56	4.42	Very High

➤ *Level of Work Performance*

Being reflected in Table 2 is the Level of Work Performance of commissioned officers in the Province of Agusan del Sur. The overall mean score was 4.42 labelled as very high. The very high-level result means that work performance of commissioned officers in the Province of Agusan del Sur is always manifested.

Data revealed that the mean scores among the indicators are all in the same category as very high level. In fact, among the 3 indicators of work performance, Task Performance Scale obtained the highest mean score of 4.48 while Contextual Performance Scale and Counter Productive Work Behavior obtained mean scores of 4.40 to 4.39 respectively.

Table 2

Level of Work Performance of the Commissioned Officers

Indicator	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Task Performance Scale	0.60	4.48	Very High
Contextual Performance Scale	0.59	4.40	Very High
Counter Productive Work Behavior	0.61	4.39	Very High
Overall	0.55	4.42	Very High

➤ *Level of Work Values*

Level of Work values is reflected in Table 3. It can be seen in the table that the overall mean score is 4.42. The overall mean score was described to be a very high level of Work Values, which means that the commissioned officers are always have the extent of Work Values in their work. There were 51 items of Work Values in this study. And, all items were described as very high level. One item got the highest mean score which is “Feeling that I am part of the PNP organization” having a mean ration of 4.49 or very high. “Working at a career that permits me to spend time with my family” has the mean ration of 4.42 which got the lowest mean score.

Table 3

The Extent of Work Values among Commissioned Officer

Item	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Having a superior who is both fair and considerate	0.67	4.43	Very High
Having a lot of obligation on my job.	0.69	4.42	Very High
Working on something that matters.	0.66	4.44	Very High
Being able to put my skills to good use on the job	0.70	4.45	Very High
Having the ability to produce high-quality work	0.68	4.43	Very High
Being able to advance in my career	0.69	4.43	Very High
Being able to lend a hand to others.	0.68	4.46	Very High
Enjoying my authority	0.72	4.40	Very High
Being able to try out different methods of performing my job	0.68	4.46	Very High
Appreciating the benefits of being a member of the PNP organization	0.69	4.48	Very High

Being able to publicly express my lifestyle.	0.78	4.34	Very High
Possessing the opportunity for personal development.	0.75	4.38	Very High
Being strength to the PNP organization.	0.74	4.42	Very High
Having the ability to take risks in my work	0.74	4.41	Very High
Working with people I like and respect	0.72	4.39	Very High
Being able to get along with my co-workers	0.68	4.47	Very High
Being able to work in a pleasant environment.	0.68	4.47	Very High
Performing a wide range of tasks	0.69	4.39	Very High
Being aware that being a PNP officer provides me with a stable job.	0.70	4.44	Very High
Being proud for being a PNP officer.	0.71	4.47	Very High
Receiving words of encouragement and motivation from my co- police officers.	0.72	4.39	Very High
Receiving an encouragement and feedback from my co-workers.	0.74	4.43	Very High
Having the freedom to freely and creatively express myself.	0.75	4.39	Very High
Considering my work for extra hours or on weekends as advantageous.	0.76	4.38	Very High
Working for an organization that has good work ethics	0.73	4.39	Very High
Not being held responsible for the actions of others.	0.79	4.35	Very High
Performing important tasks.	0.70	4.47	Very High
Being able to apply what I've learned on the job.	0.76	4.43	Very High
Feeling proud of myself for a job well done.	0.74	4.47	Very High
Possessing numerous advancement prospects	0.76	4.45	Very High

Being able to make a positive contribution to society	0.69	4.47	Very High
Possessing the ability to influence people	0.71	4.39	Very High
Having a lot of freedom in my work	0.81	4.35	Very High
Having a steady source of income	0.76	4.40	Very High
Participating in social and recreational activities with coworkers	0.74	4.46	Very High
Being able to live a life that isn't solely dedicated to work	0.84	4.32	Very High
Working for an organization that cares about its people	0.72	4.46	Very High
Having the opportunity to learn and progress in my work	0.74	4.43	Very High
Being aware that I am well-liked by my co-workers	0.74	4.40	Very High
Having a career that is both challenging and exciting	0.76	4.42	Very High
Feeling that I am part of the PNP organization.	0.76	4.49	Very High
Working in a pleasant environment	0.70	4.44	Very High
Performing a set of jobs at work	1.39	4.52	Very High
Being able to be proud of my organizations place in the industry	0.70	4.34	Very High
Being acknowledged for my efforts	0.69	4.30	Very High
Having a stable employment situation	0.67	4.35	Very High
Receiving feedback on my job from my superior.	0.70	4.38	Very High
Being able to come up with new and unique ideas	0.70	4.43	Very High
Working at a career that permits me to spend time with my family.	0.85	4.22	Very High
Working for an organization that makes a positive impact on society	0.70	4.46	Very High

Having a superior officer that is worth to be respected.	0.72	4.43	Very High
Overall	0.55	4.42	Very High

➤ *Significance on the Relationship between Professionalism and Work Performance of the Commissioned Officers*

Data outputs of the significant relationship tests between professionalism and work performance are displayed in Table 4. The overall coefficient of correlation is .845 with a p-value of .000, described as a significant degree of correlation because the p-value is lesser than the value of 0.05 level of significance in the study.

The indicators of professionalism correlated with the indicators of work performance yielded the following results: Leader/Communicator correlated with Task Performance Scale, Contextual Performance Scale and Counter Productive Work Behavior yielded an overall r= .727 at p-value ≤ 0.05. Leader/Conflict Resolver correlated with Task Performance Scale, Contextual Performance Scale and Counter Productive

Work Behavior yielded an overall r= .762 at p-value ≤ 0.05. Positive/Goal Oriented correlated with Task Performance Scale, Contextual Performance Scale and Counter Productive Work Behavior yielded an overall r= .760 at p-value ≤ 0.05. Worker/Prepared correlated with Task Performance Scale, Contextual Performance Scale and Counter Productive Work Behavior yielded an overall r= .702 at p-value ≤ 0.05. Miscellaneous correlated with Task Performance Scale, Contextual Performance Scale and Counter Productive Work Behavior yielded an overall r= .786 at p-value ≤ 0.05.

Moreover, the correlation test between the indicators of professionalism and work performance yielded the following: Task Performance Scale link with leader/communicator, leader/conflict resolver, positive /goal oriented, work/prepared and Miscellaneous with an overall r= .802 at p-value ≤ 0.05. Contextual Performance Scale link with leader/communicator, leader/conflict resolver, positive /goal oriented, work/prepared and Miscellaneous with an overall r= .787 at p-value ≤ 0.05. Counter Productive Work behavior link with leader/communicator, leader/conflict resolver, positive /goal oriented, work/prepared and Miscellaneous with an overall r= .749 at p-value ≤ 0.05

Table 4

Significance on the Relationship between Professionalism and Work Performance of the Commissioned Officers

Professionalism	Work Performance			
	Task Performance Scale	Contextual Performance Scale	Counter Productive Work Behavior	Overall
Leader/Communicator	.674** .000	.636** .000	.680** .000	.727** .000
Leader/Conflict Resolver	.697** .000	.693** .000	.695** .000	.762** .000
Positive/Goal Oriented	.712** .000	.703** .000	.665** .000	.760** .000
Worker/Prepared	.682** .000	.682** .000	.558** .000	.702** .000
Miscellaneous	.745** .000	.729** .000	.678** .000	.786** .000
Overall	.802** .000	.787** .000	.749** .000	.854** .000

➤ *Significance on the Relationship between Professionalism and Work Values*

Table 5 shows the result of the significant relationship between professionalism and work values. The data in the table reveals that the indicators of professionalism such as leader/communicator, leader/conflict resolver, positive /goal oriented, work/prepared and miscellaneous significantly correlate with work values. As a result, professionalism when correlated with work values yielded an overall r = .786 with p-value ≤ 0.05. Therefore, the two variables are significantly related to each other.

Table 5

Significance on the Relationship between Professionalism and Work Values among Subordinates

Professionalism	Work Values
Leader/Communicator	.670** .000
Leader/Conflict Resolver	.669** .000
Positive/Goal Oriented	.708** .000
Worker/Prepared	.649** .000
Miscellaneous	.743** .000
Overall	.786** .000

➤ *Significance on the Relationship between Work Values among Subordinates and Work Performance of the Commissioned Officers*

Table 6 contains the significant relationship between work values and work performance. All 3 indicators of work engagement; task performance scale, contextual performance

scale and counterproductive behavior are significantly related to work values with a p-value ≤ 0.05 , with $r = .802, .775, .796$ respectively. Results yielded an overall $r = .868$ with p-value ≤ 0.05 , therefore work values is significantly related to work performance.

Table 6

Significance on the Relationship between Work Values among Subordinates and Work Performance of the Commissioned Officers

	Work Performance			
	Task Performance Scale	Contextual Performance Scale	Counter Productive Work Behavior	Overall
Work Values	.802**	.775**	.798**	.868**
	.000	.000	.000	.000

➤ *Mediation Analysis of the Three Variables*

Data was analyzed with linear regression method as input to the mediation analysis using the path approach. Mediation analysis developed by Baron and Kenny (2001) is the mediating effect of a third variable in the relationship between two variables.

There are four steps to be met for a third variable to be acting as a mediator. In Table 7, these are categorized as steps 1 to 4. In step 1, professionalism as the independent variable (IV) significantly predicts work performance, which in this study's dependent variable (DV). In step 2, professionalism significantly predicts work values, the mediator variable (M). In step 3, Work values significantly predicts work performance. Since the three steps (paths a, b and c) are significant, further mediation analysis through path analysis is warranted to assess the significance of mediation effect. If the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable becomes non-significant at the final step of the analysis, full mediation will be achieved. It means all the effects are mediated by the mediator variable.

In addition, if the regression coefficient is substantially reduced at the final step but remains significant, only partial mediation is obtained, which implies that part of the independent variable (Professionalism) is mediated by the mediator (Work Values) but other parts are either direct or mediated by other variables that are not included in the model. In this case, as gleaned in step 4 (denoted as c'), the effect of professionalism on work performance was found to decrease after mediated by work values. Thus, partial mediation took place since the effect was found to be significant at $p < 0.05$ level.

The figure also shows the results of the computation of the effect size in the mediation test conducted between the three variables. The effect size measures how much of the effect of professionalism and work performance of commissioned officers can be attributed to the indirect path. The direct effect value of 0.759 is the beta of professionalism towards work values. The indirect effect value of 0.437 is the beta of professionalism towards work performance with work values included in the regression. The direct effect value of 0.519 is the beta between work values and work performance.

Table 7

Mediating Effect : Path Analysis (Partial Mediation)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
MV	<---	IV	.759	.035	21.970	***	
DV	<---	IV	.437	.037	11.656	***	
DV	<---	MV	.519	.039	13.378	***	

IV. CONCLUSION

With considerations on the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The findings of this study unambiguously confirm the assumptions about the mediating effect of work values of the PNP personnel on the relationship between professionalism and work performance. The findings are interpreted as a general acceptance of this assumption. Hence, the findings provide evidence that the consideration of professionalism is relevant for research on work performance; professionalism and work values; and work values and work performance. The respondents are agreeable with the idea that professionalism is important in work performance. In effect, the respondents exhibit a very

high level of professionalism, very high level on work performance and very high level of work values.

The findings were in support of the anchored theory and practice of professionalism propounded Novice to Expert theory of Benner (1984) and the Sociotechnical systems theory by (Trist & Bamforth, 1951). For this reason, work values significantly mediate the relationship between professionalism and work performance. The theory cited above discussed the association among the variables used in the study. Thus, these theories are contradicted in the present investigation since it deals with the mediating effect of work values of Police Commissioned Officers on the relationship between professionalism and work performance.

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